

Deliverable D1.3:

QC/QA procedures for greenhouse gases measurements

Document information

Project Acronym	NuClim
Project Title	Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG emission estimates
EC grant agreement No.	101166515
Project starting / end date	1st September 2024 – 31 August 2028
Work Package No.	1
Work Package Title	Nuclear and ancillary measurements
Deliverable No.	1.3
Deliverable Title	Report on QC/QC procedures for greenhouse gases measurements
Lead Beneficiary	FMI
Contractual Delivery Date	M12 (2025-08-31)
Actual Delivery Date	M15 (2025-11-26)
Type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Authors	Juha Hatakka
To be cited as	
Disclaimer	This document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Document status

Date	By	Description
25.11.2025	Juha Hatakka	Initial version
26.11.2025	Susana Barbosa	Review

Project executive summary

Radon is a unique atmospheric tracer. High-quality direct and indirect measurements of radon concentration can advance climate and atmospheric sciences, radiation protection and nuclear surveillance. These observations will reduce uncertainty in baseline characterisation of European greenhouse gas (GHG) levels and assist in environmental studies. The EU-funded NuClim project aims to investigate the influence of terrestrial factors on air masses, measure pollution events and explore the impact of natural planktonic communities on GHG emissions. Additionally, it will analyse marine boundary layer clouds and aerosols, and study wet deposition and meteorological processes affecting ambient gamma dose rates for nuclear surveillance networks.

Deliverable executive summary

This document presents quality control procedures applied to the greenhouse gases measurements collected by FMI in the scope of the NuClim campaign at the Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) station in Graciosa island, Azores. The processing steps are developed and implemented by FMI to ensure the high quality of the greenhouse gas measurements. The deliverable summarizes the system set-up, operation and data processing. The data analysis and quality control is performed according to ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation System) protocols and methods where applicable.

Glossary

ARM	Atmospheric Radiation Measurement
ENA	Eastern North Atlantic
FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute's
GHG	Greenhouse gases
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
LTT	Long Term Target
STT	Short Term Target
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	7
Measurement set-up	7
Calibration and maintenance.....	7
Data processing.....	8
Data quality control.....	9
References.....	13

Introduction

Quality control (QC) and quality assurance (QA) are important to ensure high-quality measurement results. For greenhouse gases (GHG) these criteria are compatibility goals set by the WMO: 0.1 ppm in the northern hemisphere for carbon dioxide, and 2 ppb for methane. This is achievable by proper measurement setup, calibration gases that are traceable to the WMO scales, regular calibrations, and traceable data processing.

This document presents the steps that are taken within NuClim to ensure the high quality of the greenhouse gas measurements. The system set-up, operation and data processing is according to ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation System) protocols and methods (see references) where applicable.

The instruments and their set-up are described in a more detailed way in deliverable D1.1 (“Field campaign report”).

Measurement set-up

A GHG measurement system was installed to the Finnish Meteorological Institute's (FMI) measurement container at the Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) ARM facility in May 2025. The system (Fig. 1) is based on a cavity ringdown spectrometer (Picarro G2401), which measures CO₂, CH₄, CO and water vapor. Sample air is dried (and cylinder air moisturized) with a nafion dryer. The system has five target/calibration gas cylinders, filled and calibrated (mixing ratios assigned) by the FMI.

Auxiliary (diagnostic) measurements comprise two differential pressure, a sample air flow, and a container temperature sensors. One of the differential pressure sensors (marked as p1 in Fig. 1) is used to flag out the times when there is no flow in the main line, the other to check proper working of the vacuum pump. A program running on the instrument's embedded computer collects and saves this data as one-minute averages, and it is also controlling sample valve position. All the data, i.e. files produced by the instrument and auxiliary data files, are fetched from the station ca. every 3 hours to FMI via a 4G-router.

Calibration and maintenance

Three of the cylinders are used for calibration, which is made automatically every 15 days. Also the other two cylinders, called short term target (STT) and long term target (LTT), are measured during the calibration, and in addition the STT cylinder is measured every 15 hours for 20 minutes to follow instrument's stability. During calibration all the calibration cylinders are measured three times ("cycles") for 25 minutes each. STT is measured at the beginning and end of the calibration, and LTT once at the end of the calibration (before STT) also for 25 minutes each.

As long as nothing breaks down, the system requires practically no maintenance. Due to higher gas consumption of the STT cylinder, it must be changed every two years or so before reaching 30 bar pressure. All the cylinders should be recalibrated ca. every three years. "Final" results can be calculated only after recalibration of the calibration cylinders, as mixing ratios within cylinders can change with time. Usually, however, this change is significant only for CO.

NuClim Graciosa Picarro GHG System Schematic

Fig 1. FMI's Graciosa GHG system schematic

Data processing

Data processing is made at FMI for the data files fetched automatically from the station. Auxiliary one minute average data is stored to a database table. Instrument's "raw" data files, which contain ca. 20 measurements for every component in a minute, are calculated to one-minute averages together with standard deviations for mixing ratios and stored to a database table.

Data is automatically flagged based on the instrument's internal diagnostic value ("ALARM_STATUS") and auxiliary data as invalid if so indicated. Also stabilization/flush periods (time after a port change) are automatically flagged. Manual flagging is also made to this data by visually inspecting it for anomalies.

One-minute raw averages are further processed to one-minute results by first calculating dry mixing ratios and applying calibration equations to these values. Results are stored to another database table, from which one-hour averages are calculated and stored to a separate database table.

Calibration data is processed the same way to one minute-raw averages, after which dry mixing ratios are calculated for them (as nafion moisturizes air from the cylinders). First calibration cycle is also processed, but its results are not used (flushing period). Averages for the other two cycles are calculated, and linear fit is made for both of them. The factors of these equations for the two cycles are averaged, and interpolated between calibrations. After a calibration all the results are recalculated between it and the previous calibration.

Data quality control

Automatic flagging catches most of the periods when data is invalid for system and instrument dependent reasons. However, visual inspection of the data is required for finding out other possible invalid data periods/values. In addition, if "background" mixing ratios (i.e. with local events removed) are wanted, these periods must be determined based at least partially on other, "external" data. Wind speed and direction, when flights are arriving/departing to/from the nearby airport, radon concentration, carbon monoxide mixing ratio and back trajectories (if available) are useful for this. One such example period is shown in Fig 2., during which high and variable CO₂, CH₄ and CO mixing ratios were detected together with higher than normal radon concentration indicating local ("non-background") sources.

Fig 2. Hourly averages of CO₂, CH₄, CO, and radon concentrations Oct 7 - 12, 2025.

Short term target cylinder measurements are used to check how the instrument itself is working. Instrument drift can be determined based on "raw" (uncalibrated) averages calculated from the values produced by the instrument. See Fig. 3 as an example of this drift and the calibrated mixing ratios for CO₂. One of the reasons for doing calibrations rather frequently is to compensate for this drift.

Fig 3. STT cylinder measurement results for CO₂ (in ppm). Assigned mixing ratio is some 0.02 ppm higher than average calculated based on calibrations.

Corresponding plot for the LTT cylinder is presented in Fig 4. As this cylinder is measured only during calibrations, it gives an indication of how stable mixing ratios are in calibration and LTT cylinders.

Fig 4. LTT cylinder measurement results for CO_2 (in ppm). Error bars in the left plot indicate one standard deviation of the mean.

Similar plots for CH_4 are presented in Figs. 5 and 6.

Fig 5. STT cylinder measurement results for CH_4 (in ppb).

Fig 6. LTT cylinder measurement results for CH₄ (in ppb). Error bars in the left plot indicate one standard deviation of the mean.

Calibrated STT and LTT cylinder results (average and standard deviation), and their difference to assigned cylinder mixing ratio, give a good indication of stability of the instrument, possible drift in cylinder mixing ratios, and quality of the data. These results can also be used as a factor in total uncertainty estimate together with e.g. calibration cylinder mixing ratio uncertainty.

References

Hazan, L., Tarniewicz, J., Ramonet, M., Laurent, O., and Abbaris, A.: Automatic processing of atmospheric CO₂ and CH₄ mole fractions at the ICOS Atmosphere Thematic Centre, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 4719–4736, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-4719-2016>, 2016.

Yver-Kwok, C., Philippon, C., Bergamaschi, P., Biermann, T., Calzolari, F., Chen, H., Conil, S., Cristofanelli, P., Delmotte, M., Hatakka, J., Heliasz, M., Hermansen, O., Komínková, K., Kubistin, D., Kumps, N., Laurent, O., Laurila, T., Lehner, I., Levula, J., Lindauer, M., Lopez, M., Mammarella, I., Manca, G., Marklund, P., Metzger, J.-M., Mölder, M., Platt, S. M., Ramonet, M., Rivier, L., Scheeren, B., Sha, M. K., Smith, P., Steinbacher, M., Vítková, G., and Wyss, S.: Evaluation and optimization of ICOS atmosphere station data as part of the labeling process, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 89–116, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-89-2021>, 2021.